

***CitRWP* May Not Be the Major or Only Major Gene That Regulates Apomixis in *Citrus* and Its Close Related Genus**

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Abstract

Background: Nucellar embryony in citrus and its closely related genera is a form of apomixis that interferes with crossbreeding and impacts genetic evolution and taxonomy in citrus. Numerous hypotheses have been proposed regarding the genetic regulation of apomixis in citrus and its close relatives; however, none have identified the precise regulatory sequence until the recent discovery of the candidate gene, *citRWP*. Nevertheless, the evidence supporting *citRWP* as the primary or sole regulatory gene remains inconclusive.

Results: First, the M/P (Monoembryonic/Polyembryonic) marker, designed based on the upstream sequence of *citRWP*, was used to assess whether the marker exhibited consistent segregation across different embryonic genotypes. Results showed that all sweet orange selections, whether monoembryonic or polyembryonic, contained the P-marker. However, the P-marker was not detected in polyembryonic Poncirus, and a novel band pattern appeared in nine polyembryonic progenies of *W-Murcott* × *Flying Dragon* trifoliolate orange. Subsequently, *CitRWP* expression levels were analyzed using RT-PCR and Real-time RT-PCR. RT-PCR revealed that *CitRWP* was expressed in the ovules of all tested mono- or poly-embryonic varieties. Real-time RT-PCR results for ovules were consistent with those from RT-PCR, with the lowest expression observed in monoembryonic pummelo and no significant difference between polyembryonic and monoembryonic sweet orange cultivars. In the hybrid offsprings, the expression of the *CitRWP* gene showed an extreme two-stage differentiation. In young leaf and ovule of polyembryonic and monoembryonic sweet orange cultivars, the expression of the *CitRWP* gene were different, with a higher expression level in young leaf and a lower expression level in ovule of polyembryonic cultivars. Finally, *CitRWP* cDNA sequences from ovules were cloned and sequenced, revealing significant variation in Poncirus, including SNPs in the start or stop codon and fragment insertions/deletions that led to incorrect translation. Similar variations were also observed in monoembryonic/polyembryonic sweet orange cultivars and pummelo varieties.

Conclusion and Perspectives: *CitRWP* was not consistently distributed or expressed across the different embryonic genotypes tested, suggesting it may not be the primary or sole gene regulating apomixis in citrus and its close relatives. To improve our understanding of the complex mechanisms governing nucellar embryony in citrus, a broader range of genotypes and additional candidate genes should be investigated.

Keywords: *Citrus*, Apomixis, Nucellar embryony, *CitRWP*, cDNA clone

1. Background

Citrus and its closely related genus have rich germplasm resources. They originated and are distributed in a broad area from East Asia to Australia [1]. *Citrus* is the most widely planted fruit tree in the world, and as its closely related genus, *Poncirus* and its hybrids are the most widely used rootstocks. A majority of cultivated *Citrus* varieties are obtained from natural resource exploration and bud sport selection [1,2]. Because many varieties, such as sweet orange, grapefruit, and lemon, produce polyembryonic seeds—usually with one zygotic embryo and many nucellar embryos, or only nucellar embryos within a seed—it is difficult to obtain hybrid seedlings when these varieties are used as the female parent. Thus, nucellar embryony interference has become an important factor that hinders systematic and targeted cross-breeding of *Citrus*.

Nucellar embryony is a type of apomixis. According to the origin of the embryo, apomixis can be divided into two types: one is gametophytic apomixis, where the embryo is formed by an undiminished embryo sac, and the other is sporophytic apomixis, where embryos are formed directly by somatic cells. *Citrus* nucellar embryony belongs to the latter [3]. Many recent research advances on apomixis are mainly focused on gametophytic apomixis [4], and genes controlling the production of unreduced gametes have been discovered [5]. It has been reported that three key genes control the meiosis process, and apomictic seeds have been successfully obtained in rice by mutating these genes together to construct an artificial *MIME* mutant (*Mitosis instead of Meiosis*) [6,7].

Compared with gametophytic apomixis created by *MIME*, sporophytic apomixis, as represented by *Citrus*, has significantly different origins and genetic mechanisms, and its formation is relatively simpler in terms of materials acquisition, research basis, and genetic control processes [8]. In the process of transferring apomixis traits to crops, sporophytic apomixis might provide a new supplementary approach for those species to obtain apomixis where it is difficult to achieve through the construction of *MIME*.

Citrus nucellar embryony begins with the invasion of nucellar tissues into the embryo sac. Following this, fertilization and endosperm development further stimulate the growth of nucellar embryos, with the endosperm providing nutrients for the subsequent growth of somatic embryos [9,10]. *Citrus* nucellar embryony displays a simple segregation ratio in segregating populations, which aligns with *G.J. Mendel's* classic genetic law of qualitative traits. Several theoretical hypotheses have been proposed to explain the regulation of *Citrus* nucellar embryos, including the single-gene hypothesis [11], a single major gene with minor polygenes [12], and the double-gene hypothesis [13]. However, contradictory results have been found for some of these hypotheses. For the single-gene hypothesis, according to Mendel's Law of Segregation, only polyembryonic offspring or a half polyembryonic and half monoembryonic ratio should appear in test cross combinations of monoembryonic and polyembryonic genotypes. Nevertheless, different segregation ratios have been observed in various hybridization populations. Overall, a gap remains between these hypotheses and manipulatable gene sequences.

In recent years, progress has been made toward manipulatable gene sequences. Garcia et al. identified six *QTLs* that control apomixis in *Citrus* [14], and Kepiro and Roose reported five candidate *AFLP* markers closely linked to polyembryonic *Poncirus* [15]. Nakano et al. identified *SNP* and *CAPS* markers that co-segregate with polyembryonic varieties by screening in the flanking region of polyembryonic sites, using these markers to localize a polyembryony control region containing a 380 kbp sequence with 70 predicted open reading frames

(*ORFs*) [16,17]. Shimada et al. further tested this region [18]. They designed a *DNA microarray* to examine gene expression for all *ORFs* within the polyembryony control region and screened a candidate gene, *CitRKDI*, which was tested using *RNAi* silencing in a polyembryonic sweet orange variety. Meanwhile, an *M/P* marker was designed for the presence/absence of *MITE* insertion in the promoter region of *CitRKDI*. A similar result was reported by Wang et al. [19], who narrowed the polyembryony control region to 80 kbp, which contains 11 candidate genes. After analyzing the expression of these genes, they suggested that *CitRWP*, with *MITE* insertion in the promoter region, was a key candidate gene controlling *Citrus* somatic embryogenesis. Since the sequence of *CitRWP* and *CitRKDI* was the same, this gene is referred to as *CitRWP* hereafter.

However, the supporting evidence for considering *CitRWP* as the major or only major gene is still limited. *CitRWP* encodes an *RWP-RK domain*-containing protein similar to the *Arabidopsis RKD* family of proteins [19]. This protein is known to regulate egg cell-related genes in *Arabidopsis* [20]. However, no nucellar embryony or polyembryony has been reported in *Arabidopsis* thus far. While gene expression was found to correlate with nucellar embryony in *Citrus* materials with similar genetic backgrounds, it remains to be seen if this correlation could be identified in genetically diverse genotypes. For a gene to be considered a viable target for genetic modification in a new genetic background, such as cereal crops, it must be evaluated in a closely related genus where similar apomixis genes and regulatory mechanisms may exist. Shimada et al. attempted to knock out *CitRWP* using antisense-overexpression in a polyembryonic sweet orange, but only one genetically modified plant exhibited a monoembryonic trait [18]. Somatic mutation is common in *Citrus*, especially under stress conditions like tissue culture, making it difficult to determine if the monoembryonic change resulted from the *CitRWP* knockout or mutations in other genes.

To successfully and effectively harness *CitRWP* in other crops, further evaluation of the gene function of *CitRWP* is necessary. We conducted this study using different embryonic genotypes with both similar and highly diverse genetic backgrounds, focusing on three aspects: *M/P* marker analysis in the genome, relative expression detection, and *cDNA* cloning and sequencing.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant Materials

Different Embryonic Materials: All testing materials in this experiment were planted at the *Citrus Research Institute*, Southwest University, Chongqing, China. The type of embryony is shown in Table 1.

Ovules Preparation: Ovaries at blossom time or 1~2 days after flowering (*DAF*) were collected. They were cut into halves, and ovules were stripped out as cleanly as possible, immediately placed in liquid nitrogen, and stored at -80°C for *RNA* isolation.

DNA Preparation: Young leaves were used to extract total *DNA* using the *CTAB* method. After *DNA* was precipitated with isopropanol and dissolved in water, *RNaseA* was added at a final concentration of $20\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ and incubated at 37°C for 1 hour. *DNA* concentration and quality were measured with a fluorometer (*Bio-Rad*, San Francisco, CA, USA) in combination with agarose gel electrophoresis.

RNA Extraction: Total *RNA* was extracted using the *EASYspin Plant RNA Rapid Extraction Kit* (Biomed, Beijing, China) from the prepared plant materials above. *RNA* integrity was checked with 1.0% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.

cDNA Preparation: The first-strand *cDNA* was synthesized from intact *RNA* using the *HiScript II Q RT SuperMix for qPCR (+ gDNA wiper)* (Vazyme, China) kit, following the manufacturer's instructions. The products were stored at -20°C for further use.

Common name	Scientific name	Embryony type
Meiwa kumquat	<i>Fortunella. rassifolia</i>	Polyembryonic
Wangcang daye trifoliolate orange	<i>Poncirus. trifoliolate</i>	Polyembryonic
74-1 trifoliolate orange	<i>Poncirus. trifoliata</i>	Polyembryonic
Flying dragon trifoliolate orange	<i>Poncirus. trifoliata var. Monstrosa</i>	Polyembryonic
Tarocco blood orange	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	Polyembryonic
Hamlin sweet orange	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	Polyembryonic
Licheng No. 2 sweet orange	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	Monoembryonic
Masai sweet orange	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	Monoembryonic
Tiandan sweet orange	<i>Citrus sinensis (L.) Osbeck</i>	Monoembryonic
Daidai sour orange	<i>Citrus aurantium (L.) cv. amara</i>	Polyembryonic
W-Murcott tangor	<i>Citrus reticulata Blanco cv. W-Murcott</i>	Polyembryonic
Ponkan	<i>Citrus reticulata Blanco</i>	Polyembryonic
Clementina	<i>Citrus clementina Hort</i>	Monoembryonic
Longan pummelo	<i>Citrus grandis Osbeck</i>	Monoembryonic
Banpeiyu pummelo	<i>Citrus grandis Osbeck</i>	Monoembryonic

Table 1. Embryony type of tested materials

2.2 M/P Marker Detection

The *M/P* marker primers were synthesized according to Shimada [20]. The primer sequences were 5'-tctggtcattgagaatcc-3' and 5'-ctgaccaccaggcaacacacac-3'.

The *PCR* reaction was performed in a 20 μL volume, consisting of approximately 80 ng of template genomic *DNA*, 0.2 mM *dNTPs*, 0.2 μM forward and reverse primers, 1 \times *PCR* buffer, 2.0 mM magnesium chloride, and 1U *Taq DNA polymerase*. The amplification procedure was as follows: 94 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 min; 10 cycles of 94 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 s, 64 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 40 s, and 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 s; followed by 23 cycles of 94 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 s, 58 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 40 s, and 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 s; and a final extension at 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min. *PCR* reactions were performed on a *Biometra T1 thermocycler* (Norwalk, CT, USA). The *PCR* products were analyzed by 1.5% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.

2.3 RT-PCR and Real-time RT-PCR Detection

RT-PCR: The *RT-PCR* reaction was performed in a *GeneAmp PCR System* (*Applied Biosystems*, USA). The primers were synthesized according to Zhang Siqi [22]. The primer sequences for *CitRWP* were 5'-CTGGCGTTCCTCGGTCACCT-3' and 5'-TGCAATGCTGGGAGTTTTCA-3'. The sequences for *Actin* were 5'-CATCCCTCAGCACCTTCC-3' and 5'-CCAACCTTAGCACTTCC-3'. The *PCR* reaction was performed in a 20 μ L volume, consisting of approximately 100 ng of template *cDNA*, 0.2 mM *dNTPs*, 0.2 μ M forward and reverse primers, 1 \times *PCR* buffer, 2.0 mM magnesium chloride, and 1U *Taq DNA polymerase*. The amplification procedure was as follows: pre-denaturation for 4 min at 94°C, denaturation for 45 s at 94°C, annealing for 45 s at 60°C, and extension for 40 s at 72°C for 40 cycles; followed by a 3 min final extension at 72°C, and storage at 4°C. The *PCR* products were analyzed by 1.5% (w/v) agarose gel electrophoresis.

Real-time RT-PCR: The Real-time *RT-PCR* was performed on an *ABI 7500* (*Applied Biosystems*). The same *cDNA* template and primer sets were used as in *RT-PCR*. The reaction system followed the instructions of the *AceQ[®] qPCR SYBR Green Master Mix* (*Vazyme*, Nanjing, China). The reaction program was as follows: 5 min at 95°C; 10 s at 95°C, 1 min at 60°C, for 40 cycles. The $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method was used to calculate relative expression levels.

2.4 CitRWP Cloning and Sequencing

cDNAs from ovules of selected polyembryonic and monoembryonic sweet orange and pummelo cultivars were used to clone the *CitRWP* full-length sequence. The primer sequences for cloning were as follows: *CLONE-F*: 5'-ATGGCGGATCCTAGGGCCAT-3', *CLONE-R*: 5'-ATGTGCTGGACTCACTAGATGA-3'. *PrimeSTAR Max DNA polymerase* (*Takara*), a fast and high-fidelity *DNA* polymerase, was used in *PCR* amplification. The *PCR* program was designed as follows: 5 min at 95°C, then 15 s at 94°C, 30 s at 58°C, 1 min at 72°C for 30 cycles; followed by a final extension of 3 min at 72°C, and storage at 4°C. The obtained product was given an A-tail and inserted into the *pGEM-T Easy Vector* (*Promega*) by the *pGEM[®]-T Easy Vector Systems* (*Promega*). The vector was then transformed into *E. coli* DH5 α (*Takara*) and screened by blue-white selection. The successful clones were picked at random and sent to *Tsingke Biological Technology* (Beijing, China) for sequencing.

3. Results

3.1 Validation of M/P markers in different embryonic genotypes

The M/P marker was designed by Shimada et al. [18]. M-marker implied monoembryonic alleles with 0.75 kb fragments, and P-marker implied polyembryonic alleles with 1.0 kb fragments. By the genotyping analysis of 95 traditional and breeding varieties, they found that the P-marker could be detected in all polyembryonic varieties, and only the M-marker could be detected in monoembryonic varieties. However, inconsistent results were observed in our study.

Firstly, the P-marker was detected in three monoembryonic sweet orange varieties (Li2, TD, MS), and their M/P patterns were the same as two polyembryonic sweet orange varieties (Tarocco blood orange and Hamlin sweet orange). Only the M-marker was detected in monoembryonic Banpeiyu pummelo and clementine mandarin (Figure 1). Sweet orange is the most planted citrus variety, and most sweet orange varieties produce

polyembryonic seeds, but monoembryonic lines are occasionally found around the world. Our monoembryonic sweet orange varieties were found during our breeding process and citrus germplasm collection and evaluation in China. They should be of somatic mutation origin. According to the results, the CitRWP of monoembryonic sweet orange should have the MITE insertions also. This is contradictory to the conclusion “polyembryonic alleles with a MITE insertion in the upstream region and monoembryonic alleles without it” proposed by Shimada et al. [18].

Figure 1. Allelic genotyping of CitRWP alleles in different embryonic sweet orange using M/P marker. The 1.0 kbp fragment represents the polyembryonic allele (P) and the 0.75 kb fragment represents the monoembryonic allele (M). Clem: Clementina, WBY: Banpeiyu pummelo, HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, Li2: Licheng No.2 sweet orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange.

Subsequently, only the M-marker was detected in different Poncirus genotypes, a closely related genus of Citrus (Figure 2). A reasonable deduction might be that the CitRWP exists in Poncirus and the gene does not contain the MITE insertion, or a huge mutation occurred upstream. The marker showed a different scenario in the offspring of W-Murcott × Flying Dragon trifoliolate orange (Figure 2). Only the M-marker was detected in all 7 progenies, while both the P-marker and M-marker were detected in 9 progenies. However, a different band pattern was found in both P-marker and M-marker progenies. Four polyembryonic genotype offspring produced the same band pattern as the seed parent W-Murcott, with a stronger M-marker band and a weaker P-marker band, and three polyembryonic progenies produced a new band pattern. The new band pattern included a stronger and longer band than the P-marker band and M-marker band.

Figure 2. Allelic genotyping of CitRWP alleles in trifoliolate orange genotypes and offsprings of W-Murcott tangor × Flying dragon trifoliolate orange using M/P marker. The 1.0 kbp fragment represents the polyembryonic allele (P) and the 0.75 kb fragment represents the monoembryonic allele (M). WCDY: Wangcang daye trifoliolate orange, 74-1: 74-1 trifoliolate orange, FLZ: Flying dragon trifoliolate orange, W-MKT: W-Murcott tangor, the remained are offsprings of Flying dragon trifoliolate orange × W-Murcott tangor polyembryonic.

3.2 CitRWP expression in different materials

Nucellar embryo initiates and develops in the ovule, and the flowering stage is the critical period for the development of the nucellar embryo, so gene expression analysis was done in ovules of different embryogenic varieties at the flowering stage. CitRWP expression was detected by RT-PCR with Actin as the reference gene. Under the same mRNA extraction and reverse transcription procedure and PCR conditions, RT-PCR revealed that CitRWP expressed in all varieties (Figure 3). Judged by the strength of the band, the expression level of monoembryonic Longan pummelo was the lowest, followed by polyembryonic Flying Dragon trifoliolate orange and Ponkan, and all the remaining samples showed very similar expression strength. No obvious difference could be discriminated between monoembryonic sweet orange varieties and polyembryonic sweet orange varieties.

Figure 3. Gene expression pattern of *CitRWP* in ovule of different embryogenic genotypes by RT-PCR. ACTIN was the reference gene. FLZ: Flying dragon trifoliolate orange, W-MKT: W-Murcott tangor, PG: Ponkan, HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, Li2: Licheng No. 2 sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, LAY: Longan pummelo.

CitRWP expression in the ovule was further checked by qRT-PCR in 2018 and 2019 (Figures 4 and 5). REVs (Relative Expression Values) of different embryonic varieties were computed with Banpeiyu pummelo as the control. Although the REVs are a bit different in two consecutive years, the trends are the same. Firstly, no significant difference was found among the REVs of polyembryonic and monoembryonic sweet oranges, although the REVs of polyembryonic sweet oranges were consistently higher than that of monoembryonic sweet oranges. In 2019, the REVs of Hamlin (the highest REV in polyembryonic sweet oranges) was 3.36 times that of Licheng No.2 (the lowest REV in monoembryonic sweet oranges), but the REV of Tarocco blood orange was only 1.1 times that of monoembryonic Masai (MS) sweet orange (Figure 5). In 2018, the REVs in monoembryonic sweet oranges were very close to each other. The REV of Hamlin was 2.01 times that of Licheng No.2, and the REV of Tarocco blood orange was only 1.67 times that of MS sweet orange (Figure 4). Secondly, except Flying Dragon trifoliolate, the REVs of all polyembryonic genotypes were higher than that of monoembryonic genotypes. The REVs of two pummelo varieties were the lowest consistently. REVs of Meiwa kumquat (JD) were the highest. Daidai sour orange and Ponkan were similar to that of polyembryonic sweet

orange Hamlin and Tarocco blood orange, while the REV of W-Murcott was similar to those of monoembryonic sweet orange (Figures 4 and 5). Thirdly, the REV of CitRWP in the polyembryonic Flying Dragon trifoliolate orange was much lower than that of the monoembryonic sweet orange and slightly higher than that of the monoembryonic Banpeiyu pummelo in 2019 (Figure 5). The REV of Flying Dragon trifoliolate orange was 5.5 times that of monoembryonic Banpeiyu pummelo, and the REV of polyembryonic sweet orange Hamlin and Tarocco blood orange was 73.1 and 46.9 times that of Banpeiyu pummelo, respectively. The REV of monoembryonic sweet orange Licheng No. 2, TD, and MS was 21.7 times, 32.14 times, and 42.9 times that of Banpeiyu pummelo, respectively. These results showed that the expression of CitRWP might not be directly related to embryonic phenotypes.

Figure 4. Relative expression of *CitRWP* in ovules of different embryonic genotypes in 2018. JD: Meiwa kumquat, DD: Daidai, HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, Li2: Licheng No. 2 sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, LAY: Longan pummelo, WBY: Banpeiyu pummelo.

Figure 5. Relative expression of *CitRWP* in ovules of different embryonic genotypes in 2019. FLZ: Flying dragon trifoliolate orange, W-MKT: W-Murcott tangor, PG: Ponkan, HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, Li2: Licheng No. 2 sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, LAY: Longan pummelo, WBY: Banpeiyu pummelo.

The ovule in citrus and its close relative genus is very tiny during flowering time and young fruit stage. It is difficult to get enough pure ovule for experiment quickly and safely. Therefore, we carried out a correlation analysis on the expression of ovule and ovary at the same period. The result showed that the *CitRWP* expression of the ovary was correlated with the ovule positively and significantly (Figure 6). Therefore, the expression in the ovary was detected in the offspring population of W-Murcott × Flying Dragon trifoliate orange. The analysis found that the *CitRWP* REV in W-Murcott was 6.43 times that of Flying Dragon trifoliate orange, and the REV of Wangcang Daye trifoliate orange and 74-1 trifoliate orange was similar to that of Flying Dragon trifoliate orange. In the hybrid offspring population, the REV of the *CitRWP* gene showed extreme two-stage differentiation, with 5 high-expressing progenies, 4 of which were higher than their female parent W-Murcott, while 9 low-expressing progenies were lower than their male parent Flying Dragon trifoliate orange. The REV of high-expressing progenies was ten or even hundreds of times that of low-expression ones. Among the tested progenies, the high-expressing lines had been recorded as polyembryonic in the embryony investigation, and the low-expression lines were monoembryonic, which indicated that the REV of *CitRWP* might correlate with the embryonic phenotype in the W-Murcott × Flying Dragon trifoliate orange hybrid offspring population (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Correlation analysis on *CitRWP* relative expression of ovule and ovary in citrus. By Pearson correlation analysis, $R=0.61$, $P=0.04^*(<0.05)$, the expression of *CitRWP* in ovary and ovules was significantly positively correlated at the 0.05 level (unilateral). FLZ: Flying dragon trifoliate orange, W-MKT: W-Murcott tangor, PG: Ponkan, HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, Li2: Licheng No. 2 sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, LAY: Longan pummelo, WBY: Banpeiyu pummelo.

In addition to testing *CitRWP* expression in the ovule, we also tested the expression in different tissues or organs such as young stem, young leaf, old leaf, and ovary of mono/polyembryonic sweet orange. Among the polyembryonic Hamlin and Tarocco blood orange, the young leaf had the highest expression value, which was slightly lower than its ovule. However, the expression value of the leaf decreased significantly after maturity. The REV in young leaves of Hamlin and Tarocco blood orange was 2.5, and 3.2 times that of its old leaves,

respectively. Among the monoembryonic sweet orange, the ovule was the part with the highest expression, and the young leaf expression value showed no significant difference with the young stem, old leaf, and ovary (Figure 8). *CitRWP* expressed in vegetative tissue, especially the young leaf in polyembryonic orange, had the highest REV, indicating that *CitRWP* was not specifically expressed in reproductive tissue.

Figure 7. Relative expression of *CitRWP* in ovary of trifoliate orange genotypes and offsprings of W-Murcott tangor \times Flying dragon trifoliate orange. WCDy: Wangcang daye trifoliate orange, 74-1:74-1 trifoliate orange, FLZ: Flying dragon trifoliate orange, W-MKT: W-Murcott tangor.

Figure 8. Relative expression of *CitRWP* in different tissues or organs of different embryonic genotypes. HML: Hamlin sweet orange, TX: Tarocco blood orange, TD: Tiandan sweet orange, MS: Masai sweet orange, WBY: Banpeiuyu pummelo.

3.3 Cloning and Sequencing of *CitRWP* from Different Embryonic Materials

cDNAs of *CitRWP* were cloned and sequenced from ovules of 3 polyembryonic *Poncirus* cultivars, 2 mono/polyembryonic sweet orange selections, and 2 monoembryonic pummelos. The CDS sequence of Cs4g05960 in sequenced sweet orange [1] was used as a standard to compare with the cloned *CitRWP* sequences. Three types of major variations were observed in the obtained sequences of polyembryonic *Poncirus*

(Figure 9). These variations appeared in almost all Poncirus cultivars with a high rate (Table 2). The *type I* variation was the deletion of a 106 bp fragment at the 406 bp position (relative to the translation start codon, the same hereinafter), and this deletion caused the CDS length to change from 1065 bp to 959 bp. The primers used for RT-PCR were found to locate in this region, so it might be one of the reasons that caused a lower REV in polyembryonic *Poncirus*. Eight in eighteen clones presented the 106 bp fragment deletion mutation. The *type II* variation was a 5-base (-TGCAG-) insertion mutation at the 774 bp position, which caused the CDS length to change from 1065 bp to 1070 bp. This variation was present in eight sequenced clones. Two types of variations coexisted in two sequenced clones, and the CDS length of these sequences was 964 bp. The length of these three CDS sequences was not an integral multiple of triplet codons, so they could not be translated normally. The *type III* variation involved mutations in the initiation codon and termination codon. This key codon change also led to mistranslation of functional proteins. In general, among the eighteen sequenced samples of *Poncirus*, only three sequenced clones could be normally translated, resulting in a normal translation rate of only 16.7%.

Figure 9. Variation position in cloned *CitRWP* cDNA sequences. Cs4g05960: *CitRWP* CDS sequence in sweet orange [10]. *CitRKD1-mg1* and *CitRKD1-mg2*: *CitRWP* cDNA sequence in Satsuma mandarin [12]. FLZ-RWP-1: Flying dragon trifoliolate orange *CitRWP* clone, 74-1-RWP-1: 74-1 trifoliolate orange *CitRWP* clone, WCDY-RWP-1: Wangcang daye trifoliolate orange *CitRWP* clone, TX-RWP-1: Tarocco blood orange *CitRWP* clone, TD-RWP-1: Tiandan sweet orange *CitRWP* clone, LAY-RWP-1: Longan pummelo *CitRWP* clone, WBY-RWP-1: Banpeiyu pummelo *CitRWP* clone. (A) type I variation (deletion of a 106bp fragment at 406bp position, relative to the start codon, the same hereinafter), (B) type II variation (insertion of 5bp -TGCAG- at 774bp position), (C) type III variation (mutations in the start-codon or stop-codon). (D) SNP at the 240bp position. All our cloned cDNA sequences were identical with *CitRKD1-mg2* (only partial clone sequencing results are shown).

Scientific name	Common name	106bp deletion at 406bp	5bp insert at 774bp	Initiation or termination codon change	Number of normal translation clones	Number of Clones with two or more mutations	Total clones	Proportion of normal translation
<i>Poncirus trifoliata</i> (L.) Raf	Flying dragon trifoliolate orange	4	4	1	1	2	8	12.50%
	Wangcang daye trifoliolate orange	2	1	0	2	1	5	20%
	74-1 trifoliolate orange	2	3	2	1	1	5	20%
<i>Citrus sinensis</i> (L.) Osbeck	Tarocco blood orange	0	1	0	4	0	5	80%
	Tiandan sweet orange	0	3	0	5	0	8	62.50%
<i>Citrus maxima</i> (Burm) Merr	Longan pummelo	0	0	0	3	0	5	100%
	Banpeiyu pummelo	1	0	0	4	0	5	80%

Table 2. variations in *citRWP* cDNA clones

Fewer variations were found in cloned *citRWP* cDNA sequences from two sweet orange cultivars and two pummelo cultivars. The *type I variation* of a 106-base deletion was found only in one sequenced clone from *Banpeiyu pummelo*. The *type II variation* of a 5-base (-TGCAG-) insertion was found only in four sequenced clones: one from polyembryonic *Tarocco blood orange* and three from monoembryonic sweet orange *TD*. No *type III variation* in initiation or termination codons was found. The overall normal translation rate was 69.6% in sweet orange and pummelo, which was higher than that in *Poncirus*. In addition, compared with *Cs4g05960*, there were five SNP sites in the sequenced pummelo clone, but they were all synonymous mutations and did not change the encoded amino acids.

4. Discussion

Nucellar embryony is widely considered a qualitative trait, and numerous theoretical hypotheses have been proposed to explain the regulation of citrus nucellar embryony [11-13]. The single-gene hypothesis explains only part of the observed embryony results. The hypothesis of two complementary dominant genes controlling apomixis in the *Citrus* and *Poncirus* genera offers a more comprehensive explanation [13]. This hypothesis can explain genotypes controlling polyembryony and monoembryony found in both natural species and artificial hybridization progenies, as well as most known hybridization outcomes. According to this hypothesis, screening both control genes simultaneously in a generalized hybrid segregation population using the Bulk Segregant Analysis (BSA) method or similar techniques can be challenging. Furthermore, in classical genetics, genes are

not directly correlated one-to-one with mRNA encoding sequences and may include regulatory sequences such as miRNAs or circRNAs. Restricting mRNA expression analysis to a specified sequence area may limit the exploration of additional regulatory possibilities.

The *CitRWP* gene has recently been identified as a candidate apomixis gene by two independent research groups [19,21]. The BSA method and subsequent gene expression analyses were pivotal in their screening process. Using BSA with RAPD markers and mapping on a linkage map population, a polyembryony locus was detected. The draft sequence corresponding to the polyembryony locus was then obtained through marker enrichment [16] and haplotype-specific physical map construction [17]. DNA microarrays were used to assess the gene expression of all ORFs within the polyembryony control region, leading to the identification of *CitRWP* as the candidate gene [18]. Wang et al. confirmed *CitRWP* as a key candidate polyembryony gene, using MITE insertion in a similar approach [22]. Initially, they identified a polyembryony-related region spanning 1.96 Mb on chromosome 4 using BSA in a segregating population of *HB pummelo* and *Fairchild mandarin*. Subsequently, the region was narrowed to ~80 kb through local association analysis with variant information from protein-coding genes using genome sequencing data from 108 accessions. Expression analysis of all candidate genes in the ~80-kb region helped identify *CitRWP*.

CitRWP contains the conserved RWP-RK domain, a characteristic feature of genes widely distributed in plants [21]. Genes with this domain fall into two subfamilies: the NLP subfamily, associated with nitrogen fixation, and the RKD subfamily, associated with plant reproduction and present in both lower and higher plants [23]. The RKD subfamily is involved in egg cell specification and differentiation [24], and *CitRWP* belongs to this subfamily, where it is also referred to as *CitRKDI* [20]. However, only a few species exhibit nucellar embryony, raising doubts about whether *CitRWP* is a major gene regulating nucellar embryony in citrus.

In this study, we examined *CitRWP* from three perspectives, but the combined data did not provide necessary and sufficient support for its role in regulating nucellar embryony in citrus, much less in *Poncirus*. Contradictory findings include *P* markers detected in monoembryonic sweet orange, no significant differences in *CitRWP* expression between monoembryonic and polyembryonic sweet oranges, and identical mRNA sequences among monoembryonic and polyembryonic sweet oranges. Similar contradictions were observed in polyembryonic *Poncirus* as well. Additionally, *CitRWP* did not receive full support as a candidate gene for nucellar embryony regulation in the offspring of apomictic tangerine × apomictic trifoliolate orange crosses [10].

Genes regulating nucellar embryony hold potential value in cross-breeding and genetic evolution research, as well as in taxonomy studies of citrus. A more valuable application of these genes may lie in the transfer of apomixis traits to other crops. However, whether genes that function as desired in citrus will exhibit similar functionality in genetically divergent backgrounds remains uncertain and requires further intensive studies.

5. Future Perspectives

While this study provides valuable insights into the role of *CitRWP* in regulating nucellar embryony, several limitations should be acknowledged. The relatively small sample size of genotypes analyzed may restrict the generalizability of our findings. Additionally, our focus on *CitRWP* may overlook other potential regulatory genes involved in apomixis. Methodological constraints inherent to BSA and expression analyses may also

affect the comprehensiveness of our results. Future research should aim to include a broader range of genotypes and explore additional candidate genes to deepen our understanding of the complex mechanisms governing nucellar embryony in citrus.

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Author's contribution

H-YH and Q-BH designed the experiments. H-YH conducted the experiments and data analysis and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Q-BH and G-ZG edited the manuscript. Z-CP, Q-BH and G-ZG constructed the offsprings of W-Murcott × Flying dragon trifoliolate orange. CY and AY helped with ovules preparation and conducted RNA preparation. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Data availability statement

The CitRWP sequence was downloaded from the citrus.hzau database (<http://citrus.hzau.edu.cn/cgi-bin/orange/gene/Cs4g05960.1>). Sequence align and analysis on DNA Star. The plant materials are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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